

Results in Brief, portraits of project innovations

Thermoplastic composite sheet

from recycled wood and biopolymers

The final product is an architectural interior wall panel mainly based on bio-based materials, in accordance with the goals of the circular economy. It is also an ideal material for the construction and building sector.

APPLICATION

Conventional High-Pressure Laminate (HPL) is widely used for **engineered decorative furniture surfaces** and wall claddings. The core of HPL sheets is made of several layers of kraft paper saturated with phenolic resin. The visual layer is a melamine-impregnated decor paper with a solid color or printed design, topped with a protective wear layer. Despite its high

performance, HPL is difficult to recycle, relatively expensive, and for some applications, over-engineered.

An alternative to such conventional systems is the BASAJAUN **bio-composite sheet** developed by Fraunhofer, Germany to potentially replace HPL as top layer for plywood. Its **recycling is easy**, it can be made of recycled materials, it is more cost efficient, and **no adhesive** is needed during hot-pressing onto plywood.

Being highly biobased it is designed for further use in **closed circular economy material loops** at the end of the building use cycle.

Finally, the plywood with a bio-composite top sheet combines good thermal properties with **long-term carbon sequestration** within the building material.

ACHIEVEMENT

A fire-retarded bio-composite top sheet based on PLA was developed for plywood as substitute for HPL. It can be produced with a 3 steps up-scaled production process. First, the production of the thermoplastic bio-composite sheet by co-rotating twin-screw compounding process, followed by flat-film extrusion. The final step consists of the hot-pressing of the sheet onto plywood without the use of any adhesive. Alternatively, the sheet can be glued onto plywood.

Fraunhofer is preparing a **demonstrator** which can be showcased at fairs and expositions as well as in the **demo buildings**.

✓ Process

- 1- Co-rotating twin-screw compounding
- 2- Flat-film extrusion
- 3- Hot-pressing onto plywood without any adhesive

TRL 7

It was found that after hot-pressing of the sheets onto plywood, ruptures were formed. These ruptures could be avoided by adding a paper layer between plywood and bio-composite sheets. The influence of the paper layer on top sheet adhesion and reaction-to-fire performance of the composite was evaluated. Values for surface adhesion were roughly in the same order for all papers tested. The requirement according to EN 312 (Particleboards; specifications; 2010) is 0.8 N/mm² for boards for interior fitments (including furniture) for use in dry conditions (type P2). It was found that the addition of the paper layer did not have a negative influence on reaction-to-fire performance.

BENEFITS

- Application for architectural interior wall panel system and interior furniture
- Non-fire-retarded version consists of almost 100% bio-based materials
- Fire resistance: material classified as V-0 at 4 mm thickness (UL94)
- Possibility to use wood waste (urea-formaldehyde bonded particle board)
- Easy to recycle
- Cost efficient
- Customisable exterior finish

CIRCULARITY

FURTHER R&D

Potential applications for the novel product can now be identified and additional tests could be performed, for example, related to mechanical and durability performance as well as recyclability of the product which is one of the main advantages.

Next Steps

- Increase biobased parts
- Production process optimisation
- Product full characterisation

CONTACT

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The BASAJAUN project has received a 10M€ grant funding from the *EU Horizon 2020 R&I programme*. It includes 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 14 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The team unites strong expertise in wood construction systems and buildings, innovative materials, architecture, forestry, digitalisation, environmental assessment and rural development. It covers regions in Northern, Central and Southern Europe.

